

Gendered Involvement in Cattle Rearing and Functional Literacy among In-School Youth in Kebbi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Livestock farming plays a critical role in the economy and livelihoods of rural communities in Nigeria, particularly in Kebbi State, where cattle rearing is a predominant activity. This study examines the gendered roles and functional literacy levels of in-school youth involved in cattle rearing, along gender dimension. Specifically, it described the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents; identified the cattle rearing activities the respondents are involved and their level involvement, evaluated the functional literacy level of the respondents. A multistage sampling procedure was used to 26 females and 177 males' respondents for the study. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics such percentages, mean score, mean and standard deviation and inferential statistic such as independent sample T-test, Pearsons Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) were used to make inference from the data. The findings reveal that many (87.2%) were males and only (12.8%) were females. The average mean age for both respondents was 15.9 ± 0.9 for female and 17 ± 1.68 years. About (50.0%) of the female respondents were in SSS one while (36.7%) of the male respondents were in SSS two. The result further showed that half (50.0%) of the female respondents were members of literacy and debating club while (23.2%) of males were members literacy and debating club. significant gender disparities, with males predominantly involved in technical and outdoor activities such as grazing ($\bar{x} = 5.92 \pm \sigma = 1.64$) and disease management ($\bar{x} = 1.00 \pm \sigma = 0.00$), while females focus on sales-related tasks like marketing milk and cheese ($\bar{x} = 6.00 \pm \sigma = 1.57$). Functional literacy levels, particularly in practical agricultural tasks such as reading veterinary instructions ($\bar{x} = 1.34 \pm \sigma = 0.93$) for females while ($\bar{x} = 1.67 \pm \sigma = 1.26$) for males, were found to be low across both genders, limiting their efficiency and productivity in livestock management. The result of hypothesis test showed that there was significant difference in involvement of male and females in cattle rearing activities ($\bar{x} = 11.89 \pm \sigma = 2.20$ for males; while, for females $\bar{x} = 10.73 \pm \sigma = 2.24$) Addressing these issues is crucial for achieving sustainable agricultural development and fostering gender equity in rural Nigeria.

Keywords: Gender roles, Functional literacy, Cattle rearing, In-school youth, Kebbi state

INTRODUCTION

Livestock production is crucial in achieving the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Rearing animals on farms is especially effective in combating hunger and poverty. As the second-largest contributor to the global agricultural economy, livestock supports improved nutrition, food security, and rural livelihoods (FAO, 2026). Livestock rearing is a cornerstone of Nigeria's agricultural sector, contributing substantially to the country's economy and Providing employment for millions of people. Among the various livestock practices, cattle rearing stands out as a critical activity due to its roles in meat, milk, and hide production, as well as its cultural significance in many Nigerian communities. Kebbi State, located in the Northwestern region of Nigeria, is particularly renowned for its vibrant cattle-rearing activities. The state's vast grazing lands, supported by the Sahelian ecological zone, provide a conducive environment for pastoral and semi-pastoral livestock systems (Kebbi State of Ministry Animal Health, Husbandry and Fisheries Development, n.d.). According to

Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), and the World Bank (2023), "When banking systems fail, livestock resources are thought of as a store of wealth. When crops are left behind, they can be relocated away from conflict, drought, and flood situations".

In rural areas, cattle rearing is often a family enterprise involving diverse roles distributed among men, women, and children. In-school youth frequently involve in cattle-rearing activities, balancing their educational pursuits with the demands of livestock management. However, the level of involvement and the types of roles performed often differ by gender, shaped by cultural norms and expectations. This dynamic emphasizes the need to appreciate how male and female youths contribute to cattle rearing and how their functional literacy skills influence their effectiveness in these roles. Functional literacy the ability to apply reading, writing, and numeracy skills to practical

tasks is particularly crucial for activities such as record-keeping, calculating feed rations, and interpreting veterinary instructions (Ibrahim, 2023).

Despite the importance of functional literacy in enhancing productivity and sustainability in livestock farming, there is limited empirical research exploring the intersection of gender roles and literacy skills among in-school youth involved in cattle rearing. This study aims to address this gap, with a focus on Kebbi State, Nigeria. While the role of livestock farming in rural economies is well-documented, there is a paucity of research on the gender-specific roles of in-school youth in cattle rearing and the functional literacy. Most studies on cattle rearing in Nigeria focus on adult pastoralists, overlooking the contributions and challenges of younger family members who often serve as informal apprentices in livestock management. Furthermore, the existing literature seldom examines how literacy skills or the lack thereof impacts the efficiency and sustainability of cattle-rearing practices among this demographic. This knowledge gap hinders the development of targeted interventions to enhance youth involvement and productivity in the livestock sector.

The study investigated the link between gendered involvement in cattle rearing and functional literacy among in-school in Kebbi State, Nigeria, it's argued that discrepancies in involvement patterns between men and women in-school youth meaningfully affect their literacy competencies. The study claims that while men dominate the physical and management components of cattle rearing, women exhibit greater involvement in literacy-related and record-keeping activities thus highlighting how gender roles shape the development of functional literacy skills within agricultural context. It is against this background the study seeks answers to the following questions.

1. What are socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents?
2. What are the gendered roles of in-school youth in cattle-rearing activities in Kebbi State?
3. What is the level of functional literacy among in-school youth, and how does it influence their performance in cattle management tasks?
4. What are the gender disparities in both roles and literacy levels and their implications for educational and agricultural development.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to assess gendered involvement in cattle rearing and

functional literacy among in-school youth Kebbi State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to;

1. describe the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents.
2. explore the roles of male and female in-school youth in cattle-rearing activities in the study area.
3. assess the functional literacy levels required for effective cattle management among in-school youth and
4. determine gender disparities in both roles and literacy levels and their implications for educational and agricultural development.

Hypotheses of the Study:

1. Null Hypothesis (Ho): There is no significant difference in the involvement of males and females in-school youth in cattle rearing.
2. Ho: There is no correlation between in-school youth's socioeconomic characteristics and their involvement in cattle rearing activities
3. There is no significant relationship between respondents' involvement in cattle rearing and their functional literacy scores.

Theoretical Framework

Gender and Development (GAD) Theory

The Gender and Development (GAD) theory provides a useful lens for analysing the gendered dimensions of cattle rearing. Unlike earlier approaches that focused solely on women's roles, GAD emphasises the relational nature of gender and seeks to understand how societal structures and power dynamics shape the experiences of both men and women (Razavi & Miller, 1995). In the context of cattle rearing and management, GAD highlights the need to tackle systemic barriers, such as unequal access to resources and education, that limit women's and girls' involvement in productive activities. By applying GAD theory, this study aims to uncover the ways in which gender norms influence the roles and responsibilities of in-school youth in cattle rearing. This approach also facilitates the identification of strategies to promote gender equity and empower both boys and girls to contribute meaningfully to livestock farming.

Human Capital Theory

According to Becker's Human Capital Theory (1964), investments in education and skill development improve economic outcomes and individual productivity. The theory emphasizes the value of functional literacy as a type of human capital that can enhance the productivity and sustainability of cattle-rearing methods in the context of this study.

By equipping in-school youth with the necessary literacy and numeracy skills, stakeholders can enhance their capacity to manage livestock

effectively and contribute to household incomes. Moreover, Human Capital Theory highlights the potential for education to break intergenerational cycles of poverty. For rural youth involved in cattle rearing, functional literacy serves not only as a tool for immediate productivity but also as a foundation for long-term socioeconomic mobility. This theoretical perspective reinforces the need for integrated educational programmes that address both academic and practical skills.

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

The study area for this research is Kebbi State, which is in the northwest of Nigeria. The state is bordered by Niger to the west, Sokoto State to the north, and Zamfara State to the east. Its predominantly agrarian, with a significant portion of

its population engaged in agricultural activities, including crop farming and livestock rearing. The state’s ecological zone, characterised by a mix of Sudan and Sahel savanna, provides an ideal environment for cattle grazing and other livestock-related activities (Kebbi State Government, n.d.).

Numerous ethnic groups, such as the Hausa, Fulani, Zabarmawas, Dakarkaris, and Kamaris, are found in Kebbi State. Many of these groups depend on cattle rearing as a primary or supplemental source of income. The education system in the state includes a mix of formal and informal structures, with numerous schools catering to in-school youth. However, the integration of functional literacy into the curriculum, particularly for agricultural practices, remains limited, creating a gap in practical skills development.

Figure 1: Map of Kebbi State, showing selected Local Government Areas

Conceptualisation, operationalisation and measurement of variables

Involvement is conceptualised as the extent to which in-school youth are involved in cattle-rearing activities and is operationalised as the number of hours the individual spent in cattle-rearing related activities. It’s also measured as a continuous variable. The ability to apply fundamental reading, writing, and math skills to practical tasks is known as functional literacy. In the context of cattle rearing,

functional literacy refers to the ability of in-school youth to apply basic reading, writing, and numeracy skills to tasks related to livestock management. A five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 to 5, was used to evaluate the respondents' literacy levels using thirteen (13) functional literacy items: never (1), less than once a month (2), less than once a week (3), at least once a week but not every day (4), and every day (5). The minimum and maximum possible scores obtainable by each respondent were 14 and

70, respectively. The mean value of the scale was calculated as $(1+2+3+4+5) \div 5 = 3.0$, which served as the benchmark for categorising respondents' functional literacy into low, moderate, and high (Ibrahim, 2023).

To ensure internal consistency and reliability of the instrument used to assess functional literacy among in-school youth involved in cattle rearing, a reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha in SPSS (version 23). The analysis was performed using listwise deletion, which excluded no cases for the dataset, confirming that all 203 respondents provided valid responses for the 13 literacy-related items. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient obtained was 0.907, while the standardized alpha was 0.904, both of which suggest excellent reliability according to George and Mallery (2010). This high alpha value suggests that the items are strongly correlated and collectively measure a single, coherent construct functional literacy in the context of cattle rearing. Thus, the research instrument can be considered both reliable and internally consistent for evaluating literacy-related competencies among youth livestock farmers.

Consequently, the item Statistics further showed that the mean scores of the literacy items ranged between 1.26 and 4.25, with standard deviations between 0.78 and 1.32. The highest mean score was recorded for "copy notes" ($M=4.25$, $SD=0.78$), demonstrating that most respondents were proficient in notetaking and classroom-based writing. Conversely, lowest mean was observed for "Fill forms"), suggesting, limited experience with administrative documentation tasks. The Scale Statistics showed a total of mean score of 27.55, with a variance of 86.55 and a standard deviation of 9.30. This spread reflects variability in respondents' functional literacy performance, pointing to differing levels of engagement with literacy tasks associated with cattle management.

Additionally, the strong reliability coefficient supports the accuracy of the functional literacy mean scores presented in Table 3, where respondents showed moderate literacy levels. Female respondents exhibited slightly higher competency in writing activities such as notetaking, while males performed better in computational engagements such as calculating feed prices and using fractions. The consistency across items suggests that these differences genuinely reflect variations in literacy skills rather than inconsistencies in measurement. In conclusion, the high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.907$) confirms that the Functional Literacy Scale used in this study is a valid and dependable tool for assessing literacy competencies among in-school youth involved in cattle rearing.

Population and Sampling

The study was carried out in Nigeria's Kebbi State. The target population consists of young people who are simultaneously enrolled in school and raising cattle. The study's respondents were chosen using a multistage sampling technique. In the initial phase, three pastoral blocks, or 60% of the total, were chosen. The availability of senior secondary schools served as the basis for this choice. These pastoral areas were Zuru, Bagudo, and Birnin Kebbi, in that order. Two Local Government Areas (LGAs) were chosen in each of the pastoral blocks, for a total of six LGAs. Ten percent of the schools were chosen at random, for a total of nineteen (19) schools. The rationale for this was based on the availability of conventional senior secondary in these pastoral blocks. Senior secondary school classes were purposefully chosen in the second stage so that most of the students were engaged in raising cattle. Registers of the chosen classes were gathered in the third phase with the consent of the corresponding principals and teachers. Cattle rearers who self-identified were counted using the class registers. Slovin's formula ($n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$) (n =number of samples, N =total population, and e =error tolerance) with a margin error of 0.05 was utilized to determine the sample size at the fourth stage. The study included 203 in-school youth, 26 of whom were female and 177 of whom were male.

Data Collection and Analysis

The study uses a mix of quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques to achieve its objectives. Structured questionnaire and interviews: Questionnaire was designed to capture quantitative data on the frequency and type of cattle-rearing activities performed by in-school youth, as well as their functional literacy levels. Semi-structured interviews provide qualitative insights into participants' experiences, challenges, and perspectives on cattle rearing and literacy. Observation of Cattle-Rearing Activities. Direct observation is used to validate self-reported data and gain a deeper understanding of the practical roles performed by youth in cattle management. The collected data is analysed using a mix of quantitative and qualitative techniques: Quantitative Analysis: Statistical tools, such as SPSS, are employed to analyse survey data. Descriptive statistics (e.g., means, frequencies) are used to summarize the roles and literacy levels of participants, while inferential statistics (e.g., t-tests, Pearsons' Product Moment Correlation (PPMC)) examine relationships between variables. Thematic Analysis: Qualitative data from interviews and observations are analysed thematically to identify recurring patterns, themes, and insights. This approach helps to contextualize the quantitative findings and provides a richer understanding of the participants' experience.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

The results presented in Table 1 show that many (87.2%) of the respondents were male, while female respondents accounted for (12.8%) of the total sample. This finding indicates that cattle rearing in the study area is male dominated, reflecting long-standing cultural traditions which men are primarily responsible for cattle management. This finding support Ibrahim (2023), who found that males were more involved in cattle rearing than their female counterparts. The result further shows the average age of female respondents was 15.9 years

(SD=0.97), compared to 17.1 years (SD=1.68) for males. Most respondents were within the 15-17 years age range, indicating that young people particularly the in-school youth are actively involved in cattle rearing, it could be likely through family or community-based activities. This corroborates with Sani *et al.* (2023), who noted the significance of young people’s involvement in rice value addition activities as a pathway for skills acquisition and economic inclusion. This result also contradicts the finding of Adetarami *et al.* (2023), who found that the average age of young rural dwellers was 32 years.

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondent according to gender

Variables	Freq	%	Mean	Std. deviation
Age (Females)			15.92	0.97
15 to 17 Years old	24	92.3		
18 to 20 Years old	2	7.7		
Males (Age)			17.10	1.68
15 to 17 Years old	109	61.6		
18 to 20 Years old	63	35.6		
21 Years and above	5	2.8		
Sex				
Females	26	12.8		
Males	177	87.2		
Level of education (Females)				
SSS One	13	50.0		
SSS Two	12	46.2		
SSS Three	1	3.8		
Males (level of education)				
SSS One	61	34.5		
SSS Two	65	36.7		
SSS Three	51	28.8		
Membership of association (Females)				
Young farmers club	2	7.7		
Literacy and Debating club	13	50.0		
Drug free club	2	7.7		
Others	9	34.6		
Males				
Young farmers club	30	16.9		
Scout club	12	6.8		
Red cross society	13	7.3		
Literacy and Debating club	41	23.2		
Drug free club	11	6.2		
Others	70	39.5		
Years of experience in cattle rearing (Females)			8.07	1.38
2 to 6 Years of cattle rearing	2	7.7		
7 to 10 years of cattle rearing	24	92.3		
Males				
2 to 6 Years of cattle rearing	18	10.2		
7 to 10 years of cattle rearing	131	74.0		
14 years and above	28	15.8		

Source: Field survey, 2022

This result aligns with the result of Oose, *et al.* (2023), who reported similar findings. The further also reveals that most female respondents were SSS one (50%) or SSS two (46.2%), while male respondents were more evenly distributed across all

secondary levels. This suggests that boys and girls have access to education, though slightly more male have advanced further, possibly due fewer domestic responsibilities. Interestingly, half of the female respondents were members of literacy and debating

clubs (50%), compared with (23.2%) of males. It indicates that female youth may be drawn to literacy-based extracurricular activities, which could enhance their skills in communication and functional literacy.

Conversely, the Table further revealed nearly all female respondents (92.3%) had between 7-10 years of experience, while males had a wider range, with (74%) in the 7–10-year category and (15.8%) having over 14 years. The difference shows that males are often socialized into cattle rearing earlier and remain involved longer than their female counterparts. It is in tandem with the finding of Ibrahim (2023), who reported that male children are socialize early into cattle rearing than female.

Gendered Involvement in Cattle Rearing among the respondents

The result presented in Table 2 reveals the analysis of mean scores for male and female respondents’ involvement in cattle-rearing activities which demonstrates significant gender disparities. Males demonstrated higher levels of involvement in activities such as turning out cattle for grazing ($\bar{x} = 5.92, \sigma = 1.64$) compared to females ($\bar{x} = 2.42, \sigma = 2.62$). Similarly, males were more involved in deworming of animals ($\bar{x} = 0.85, \sigma = 0.36$) and returning cattle to their pens ($\bar{x} = 1.20, \sigma = 0.42$), while female involvement in these tasks was negligible or non-existent.

In contrast, females showed higher involvement in sales-related activities, such as the sale of milk and

cheese ($\bar{x} = 6.00, \sigma = 1.57$), with no recorded involvement from males. Additionally, while males were more involved in grazing and disease management, females participated more in milking activities ($\bar{x} = 1.11, \sigma = 0.32$), though their involvement was still lower than males in this category ($\bar{x} = 0.68, \sigma = 0.48$). This finding agrees with Ibrahim (2023) ; Rotich (2016) and Arowolo and colleagues (2013), who submitted that females were more involved in milking and sales-related activities. These findings stress the persistence of traditional gender roles in cattle rearing, with males dominating outdoor and technical tasks, while females focus on domestic and sales-related roles. This implies male respondents spent relatively five hours per day which could affect their time for literacy-related activities.

The finding supports the finding of Kayode and Abdullateef (2023), who noted that, many children in farming households spent between 9 and 11 hours on the farm. The low level of involvement in cattle rearing by female respondents is due culture stereotype as reported by Ibrahim (2023), that Culture has restricted women to only milking and selling milk and its products, such as cheese. The finding was supported by an FGD extract thus *“Our female siblings stay with our mothers to care for our younger ones and assist in household chores.”* *“Cattle rearing requires a lot of energy and perseverance and therefore is not for the females.”* Similarly, Ibrahim (2023), in his study found that about (74.2%) of the in-school youth spent about 9 hours herding cattle.

TABLE 2: Mean scores of in-school youth involvement in cattle rearing according to their sex

Cattle rearing activities	Female		Male	
	\bar{x}	σ	\bar{x}	σ
Turning out cattle for grazing.	2.42	2.62	5.92	1.64
Observing and isolating sick animals	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00
Feeding halves of the daily concentrate ration to and fattening calves	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Watering of the animals on the grazing lands	0.61	0.49	1.02	0.19
Feed chopped green and dry fodder to penned animals	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cleaning of all the sheds and disposal of manure	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Returning cattle to their pen	0.73		1.20	0.42
	0.53			
Feeding halves of the daily concentrate ration to nursing females	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Record keeping	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Weighing of animals	0.00		0.00	0.00
	0.00			
Marketing of animals	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Deworming of animals	0.00	0.00	0.85	0.36
Trimming of hooves	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Tethering of animals	0.00		0.00	0.00
	0.00			
Deeping of animals for ectoparasite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Colostrum feeding	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Weaning	0.00		0.00	0.00
	0.00			
Identification	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Castration	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Disbudding	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Extra teat removal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Dentition and ageing	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Transport	0.00		0.00	0.00
	0.00			
Disinfection	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Quarantine	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Vaccination	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Proper time breeding	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pregnancy diagnosis	0.00		0.00	0.00
	0.00			
Insuring animal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Carcass disposal	0.00	0.00	0.71	0.45
Milking	1.11	0.32	0.68	0.48
Involve in sales of milk/ cheese	6.00		0.00	0.00
	1.57			

Source: Field survey, 2022

Mean summary of in-school youth Functional Literacy Levels

The evidence presented in Table 3 presents the mean scores of respondents' functional literacy across selected item, disaggregated by gender. The findings revealed that both female and males exhibited a moderate level of functional literacy with grand mean of 2.20, indicating that while some participants possess some literacy skills there is still room for improvement in task such as reading comprehension, writing, and numerical application related to cattle management. Across all functional literacy indicators, females recorded relatively

higher in tasks requiring writing and documentation, while males performed marginally better in tasks like numeracy and reading-related activities. For instance, females had a higher mean score in coping notes in class (mean = 4.25, SD = 0.78), compared to males (\bar{x} = 4.29; σ = 0.80), suggesting greater involvement with classroom writing. On the other hand, males scored higher in numerical and interpretive tasks, such as using calculator or calculating with calculator or computer and using calculators (\bar{x} = 3.42, σ = 0.84) and using fraction (\bar{x} = 3.48; σ = 0.94), demonstrating strong quantitative literacy among male respondents.

TABLE 3: In-school Youth Functional Literacy Mean Score

Functional literacy items	Female		Male	
	\bar{x}	σ	\bar{x}	σ
Copy notes	4.61	0.49	4.19	0.80
Used or calculated, either hand-held or computer based	3.19	1.20	3.42	0.84
Prepare charts or graphs or tables.	3.23	0.99	3.35	0.93
Calculating prices of cattle feeds.	3.00	1.09	3.33	0.90
Used or calculated fractions.	3.00	1.32	3.48	0.94
Written a letter.	1.84	1.37	1.80	1.31
Read directions or instructions on the label of cattle drug.	1.15	0.78	1.68	1.24
Read letter received for your livestock extension officer	1.34	0.93	1.67	1.26
Read manuals	1.11	0.58	1.42	1.08
Read bills, invoices, bank statements.	1.26	0.96	1.41	1.06
Read labels.	1.11	0.58	1.41	1.05

Read newspaper.	1.15	0.61	1.40	1.08
Read diagrams, maps or schematics.	1.15	0.78	1.36	1.00
Fill forms.	1.00	0.00	1.29	0.93
Grand Mean=2.20				

Source: Field survey, 2022

Reading-related activities, particular those connected to cattle management, such as reading direction on cattle drug labels and letters from livestock extension agents, showed generally low means scores for both respondents. Females scored ($\bar{x} = 1.15, \sigma = 0.78$) on reading drug labels, while males performed slightly better ($\bar{x} = 1.68, \sigma = 1.24$). Consequently, reading extension letters had a mean score of $\bar{x} = 1.34$ (females), $\bar{x} = 1.67$ (males), implying that comprehension of technical agricultural documents remains weak among the respondents in the study area. Conversely, lowest mean scores were recorded in filling-forms, readings manuals and interpreting diagrams or maps, all of which are vital in understanding modern cattle management techniques. These findings show that while the respondents can handle basic numeracy and literacy tasks, their ability to interpret, analyse and apply written agricultural information is scarce. This imply that functional literacy among the respondents is more developed in more academic context (i.e., note taking and calculations) than in applied agricultural context. This result is consistent with Chetthamrongchai, Foosiri and Jermisittiparsert (2019), who found that farmers’ accounting literacy and training significantly enhanced perceived crop yield. These findings demonstrated that functional literacy acts as bridges between agricultural knowledge and its application.

However, functional literacy is beyond reading and writing to include information literacy, the ability to locate, interpret and use agricultural information. Sang and Cheruiyot (2020), indicated that information-literate farmers in Kenya achieve better productivity outcome than those without such skills. The ability to access and interpret weather forecasts, extension bulletins and market data correlated strongly with output levels. Gong *et al.* (2024);

Wenqi and Meng (2025), in their separate studies found that farmers’ digital functional literacy, significantly improved green production efficiency and overall farm productivity. These gaps suggest that while youth possess general literacy skills, their ability to apply these skills to practical cattle-rearing tasks is limited. This disconnect may hinder their effectiveness in managing cattle enterprises and reduce their capacity to contribute to household income and productivity.

Hypotheses testing

The involvement of men and women in the rearing of cattle is not significantly different.

Levene’s Equality of Variances Test results: $F = 0.669, p = 0.414$. Because the p-value (0.414) is higher than 0.05, Levene’s test does not reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there is no violation of the presumption of equal variances between the two groups (males and females). For the t-test, we therefore continue under the assumption of equal variances. $t\text{-value} = 2.273, df = 201, \text{and } p = 0.024$ for the t-test for equality of means (assuming equal variances). We reject the null hypothesis (H_0) because the p-value (0.024) is less than 0.05. Furthermore, the p-value (0.024) shows that male and female involvement in cattle rearing differs significantly. Compared to females (mean = 10.7308), males (mean = 11.8045) are more involved in raising cattle. The conclusion that the difference is statistically significant is further supported by the fact that the mean difference is 1.07375 and the 95 percent confidence interval for the difference is (0.14215, 2.00536), which does not include zero. Consequent upon the above a significant difference exist in involvement of males and females in-school youth, with males showing a higher level of involvement.

Table 4: Independent Samples Test Result

Involvement score	Levene’s test for equality of variance		t-test for equality of means						
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
Equal variance assumed	0.669	0.414	2.273	201	0.024	1.07375	0.47246	0.14215	Upper 2.00536

Equal variance not assumed	2.058	30.887	0.048	1.07375	0.52186	0.00926	2.13824
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Source: Computed from independent samples test

There is no significant relationship between respondents’ socioeconomic characteristics and their involvement in cattle rearing activities

The results in Table 5 show that at $p \leq 0.05$ there was significant and positive relationship between some socioeconomic characteristics of both genders and years of experience in cattle rearing activities ($r=0.537$ for female; $r=0.641$ for males). It shows that years of experience in cattle rearing activities is

a significant factor to respondents’ involvement in cattle rearing activities. The coefficients of determination show that among female respondents contributed about 28% of the variance in the level of involvement among female respondents while 41% in the total variance in the level of involvement among male respondent was observed. Meaning that years of experience in cattle rearing plays a significant role in the involvement of both male and female respondents in the study area.

Table 5: Correlation analysis showing the relationship between respondents’ socioeconomic characteristics and involvement in cattle rearing activities according to gender

Variables	r	r ²	P=	Decision
Age(females)	.180	0.03	0.379	Not significant
Years of experience in cattle rearing	0.537**	0.28	0.05	Significant
Age(males)	0.115	0.01	0.126	Not significant
Years of experience in cattle rearing	0.641**	0.41	0.01	Significant

** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Computed from Correlation analysis results.

There is no significant relationship between respondents’ involvement in cattle rearing and their functional literacy score

Additionally, the evidence presented in Table 6 reveals the relationship between respondents’ level of involvement in cattle rearing activities and their functional literacy scores, disaggregated by gender. The results show a weak positive and statistically insignificant relationship between involvement in cattle rearing activities and functional literacy among female respondents ($r=0.329$; 0.101). This indicates that although female youth who involve more actively in cattle rearing activities tend to have slightly higher functional literacy levels, but the correlation is not strong enough to be statistically meaningful. The coefficient of determination showed ($r^2=0.108$) reveals that only about 10.8% of the variation in functional literacy among female in-school youth can be explained by their involvement in cattle rearing activities. This result corroborates with finding of Lungubu and Birner (2021), who reported that females’ education was among the drivers of cattle herd productivity.

Nonetheless, there was significant weak negative ($r=-0.164$; 0.029) relationship between male respondents’ level of involvement in cattle rearing activities and their functional literacy. It implies that as male continue to be involved in cattle rearing their functional literacy decreases. The r^2 (-0.026) indicates that only about 2.6% of variation in functional literacy can be explained by their involvement in cattle rearing. Despite its low magnitude, the relationship is statistically significant. The different pattern observed across genders, may reflect cultural roles and functional literacy opportunities characterised with livestock management. For female in-school youth, involvement in cattle rearing involves tasks such as marketing and financial management. While male involvement may be more physically demanding and time consuming and energy sapping which limits the time for literacy-related involvement. In essence, the results suggest that gender dynamics influence the relationship between livelihood activities and functional literacy in the study area.

Table 6. Relationship between respondents’ involvement in cattle rearing activities and their functional literacy according to gender

Variables	r	r ²	P=value	Decision
Functional literacy score (females)	0.329	0.108	0.101	NS
Functional Literacy score (Males)	-0.164*	-0.026	0.029	S

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Computed from correlation analysis results, 2022

This corroborates the findings Ma *et al.* (2024), who noted that digital literacy enhanced livelihoods resilience of livestock farmers in China pastoral areas. They also noted that literate farmers used mobile tools to tract animal health, access weather updates, and market livestock profitably. Notably, Gong *et al.* (2024), reported that literacy especially in ICT use boosted green production efficiency and reduce management losses. Similarly, Sang and Cheruiyot (2020), demonstrated that information literacy a core component of functional literacy, significantly increased productivity across agricultural systems including livestock. Farmers who could read veterinary instructions, vaccines schedules and extension leaflets manage their herd very well and suffered fewer losses.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study reveals significant gender differences and low levels of functional literacy among in-school youth involved in cattle rearing in Kebbi State, Nigeria, with males focusing on technical tasks and females focusing on sales-related roles. Based on the findings emanating from this study the following recommendations were made.

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To promote sustainable agricultural development, increase productivity and promote gender equality in cattle rearing.

- i. Gender-sensitive education and training should be created. Implement training programmes to promote gender equality in livestock production by promoting shared responsibilities and challenging traditional gender norms.
- ii. Promoting agricultural literacy in schools. Incorporate practical agricultural skills like reading veterinary instructions and calculating feed rations, into school curricula to close the gap between education and practice.
- iii. Functional Literacy Workshops. Organise community-based workshops to enhance practical skills like record-keeping, basic accounting, and technical document interpretation for in-school youth.
- iv. Community Awareness Campaigns should be created. Launch campaigns to promote equitable roles in livestock management and encourage active involvement of both male and female youth.

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